

Crop and resource management

Integrated fertilizer management

Effect of granular N fertilizers on growth and grain yield of rice

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We studied the effect of granular N fertilizers on the growth, grain yield, and nutrient use efficiency of rice under irrigated conditions during the 1991 dry season (DS) at the DRR Experimental Farm. Soil is a Vertisol with pH 8.3, CEC 49.2 meq/100 g soil, 0.01% total N (modified Kjeldahl method), and 6 ppm available P (Olsen's method). The experimental plots, except control, were fertilized uniformly with 90-26.4-41.5 kg NPK/ha.

Fertilizers studied were prilled urea (PU) of 350-400 prills/g wt, large granule urea (LGU) of 4-6 granules/g wt, urea supergranules (USG) of 1 g wt each, diammonium phosphate (DAP) of 28-32 granules/g wt, large granule diammonium phosphate (LDAP) of 7-10 granules/g wt, and single super-

Grain yield and nutrient response as influenced by granular fertilizers, 1991-92 dry season (rabi).

Treatment ¹	Grain yield (t/ha)	N response (kg grain/kg N)	Nutrient response (kg grain/kg nutrient)
Control	2.9	-	-
PU + SSP	4.8	20.8	9.3
PU + DAP	5.2	25.2	11.3
PU + LDAP	5.6	30.5	12.7
LGU + SSP	5.2	26.3	11.9
LGU + DAP	5.1	24.9	11.2
LGU + LDAP	5.5	28.8	13.0
USG + SSP	6.1	35.7	16.0
USG + LDAP	6.4	39.0	17.6
LSD (0.05)	0.4		
CV (%)	5.7		

¹All treatments, except control, received 90 kg N/ha, 26.4 kg P/ha, and 33.2 kg K/ha.

phosphate (SSP) (see table). DAP, LDAP, and SSP were applied basally; PU and LGU in two splits; and USG was placed in the root zone 7 d after transplanting.

Large granular treatments (USG + LDAP) had significant increases in growth and grain yield and were superior to all other treatments except USG + SSP. We observed promising results in all treatments with LDAP, irrespective of N source. Grain yields with LDAP

treatments were 5.5-6.4 t/ha, compared with 4.8-6.1 t/ha with SSP treatments.

The response of grain yield to N and also the unit response per kg of NPK was high in treatments receiving point placement of N as USG and basal dose of LDAP.

It can be inferred that rice responds better to granular N and P fertilizers than to PU and SSP. Placement of N as USG in the root zone and basal application of P and part of the N as LDAP gave the best results for growth, yield performance, and nutrient use efficiency in rice under DS irrigated conditions. ■

Fertilizer management—inorganic sources

Modern varieties (MVs) yield more than traditional varieties (TVs) in Cambodia regardless of fertilizer use

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Modern varieties and associated technologies were evaluated in a series of on-farm adaptive trials (OFAT) initiated by CIRP in 1990. Farmers conducted the trials using their own resources and style of crop management. They did not receive inputs or insurance against crop failure to ensure that test varieties were exposed to the same constraints they would encounter when adopted by farmers. Some farmers did not apply fertilizer or manure because the inputs were unaffordable or unavailable. Those using fertilizers applied a maximum of 60 kg N/ha and 30 kg P/ha.

Farmers were provided with 1 kg seed each of IR66, IR72, and Kru (IR13429-150-3-2-1), which had been identified as superior early rice varieties. Each farmer provided 1 kg seed of the best local short-duration variety to serve as a check.

Checks represented most of the common

Yield of IR66, IR72, and Kru compared with local checks in OFAT in 1990 WS (51 locations), 1991 DS (39 locations), 1991 WS (90 locations), and 1992 DS (80 locations).

Variety	With fertilizer		Without fertilizer	
	Yield (t/ha)	% over check	Yield (t/ha)	% over check
1990 WS				
23 locations 28 locations				
IR66	3.3	14	2.5	0
IR72	3.1	7	2.5	0
Kru	2.9	0	3.0	17
Check	2.9	0	2.5	0
1991 DS				
22 locations 17 locations				
IR66	5.4	26	3.6	3
IR72	4.9	14	3.6	3
Kru	4.8	12	3.6	3
Check	4.3	0	3.5	0
1991 WS				
60 locations 30 locations				
IR66	3.1	11	3.1	15
IR72	3.0	7	3.2	19
Kru	3.1	11	3.1	15
Check	2.8	0	2.7	0
1992 DS				
36 locations 44 locations				
IR66	5.1	24	4.3	13
IR72	4.7	15	3.9	3
Kru	4.8	17	4.1	8
Check	4.1	0	3.8	0

TVs of Cambodia. Each variety was planted in a 100-m² plot. Crops were grown under rainfed or irrigated conditions in 15 provinces. Farmers recorded variety characteristics and chose varieties on the basis of performance. In most cases, farmers chose to adopt MVs regardless of whether they used fertilizer.

IR66, IR72, and Kru outperformed checks regardless of fertilizer application (see table). The differences in yield between varieties and checks were greater in the dry season (DS) than in the wet season (WS). Yields were larger where farmers applied fertilizer.

We conclude that MVs can perform as

well as or better than TVs with and without fertilizer inputs. Farmers are more likely to adopt MVs that can adapt to a range of nutrient supply environments. In Cambodia, the use of new MVs has spread to 20,000 ha during the past 2 yr. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Adhatoda vasica (asuro): a superior indigenous green manure species for rice in the hills of Nepal

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Adhatoda vasica (asuro) is a gregarious, thickly branched, evergreen woody shrub with medicinal, pesticidal, fungicidal, and manurial properties. The nonleguminous species grows well and produces dense foliage in the warmer regions of Nepal up to elevations of 1300 m above sea level.

Farmers in the hills of Nepal traditionally use the foliage of asuro and other indigenous plants to supply nutrients for their wetbed rice nurseries. Asuro quickly decomposes when incorporated into the soil. Tissue analysis found that asuro contains 4.3% N, 0.88% P, and 4.49% K.

We studied the green manuring potential of asuro and compared it with another indigenous nonlegume,

Eupatorium odenophorium (banmara), chemical fertilizer (60-30-30 kg NPK/ha), and farmers' rate of compost (10 t/ha) in irrigated transplanted rice (Khumal-4 at Shera and Keware, Manakamana-1 at Yampaphat), during the 1991 rice season (Jun-Nov). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with five replications at each of three locations. Fresh biomass of asuro and banmara, compost, and fertilizers were incorporated into soil at puddling.

Pooled analysis of variance revealed a highly significant treatment difference for grain yield across locations. Mean yield was highest with asuro (4.8 t/ha) (see table). Banmara and chemical fertilizer showed no difference. Asuro's high yield is because of the high nutrient content in its foliage. These results agree with farmer reports that asuro is the best indigenous species for green manuring.

Hard or soft wood cuttings of asuro can be propagated easily. Asuro makes a good live fence and is a good source of nectar for honey bees. ■

Crop management

Residual effects of phosphorus on deepwater rices (DWR) submerged at intermediate water depths and by flash flooding

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We studied the effect of P fertilizer at 0, 8.8, 17.6, 26.4, and 35.2 kg P/ha on semidwarf, long-duration (165 d), photoperiod-sensitive rice cultivar CR1016 under intermediate deep water (15-50 cm) and simulated flash flooding conditions in 1987-89. Crops were sown at 400 seeds/m² at 20-cm row spacing in dry soil before the onset of monsoon rains. They were fertilized with a common basal dose of 60 kg N and 16.6 kg K/ha in the plow furrow. Soil was alluvial, sandy-clay-loam in texture, with 0.09% total N, 22 kg available P/ha, and 128 kg available K/ha.

Crops were grown in the same plots all 3 yr without disturbing the layout plan and with minimal shifting of soil across plots. P treatments in 1988 were applied to the same plots as in 1987 to study the cumulative effect of P. P fertilizer was not applied in 1989 to find out the residual effect.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design (submergence levels as main plots and P levels as subplots) with three replications. Water depth was 15-50 cm during most of the cropping period, except when flash floods were created in specially constructed cement tanks. Plants were submerged up to 80 cm for 10 d in 1987 and 1988 and partially submerged up to 70 cm for 7 d in 1989.

Grain yield decreased due to submergence. The magnitude of decrease

Comparative performance of *Adhatoda vasica* green manure with other nutrient sources at locations in Western Hills, Nepal, 1991.

Treatment	Rice yield ^a (t/ha)			
	Shera (1250 m)	Keware (1200 m)	Yampaphat (450 m)	Mean
Compost (10 t/ha)	2.7	3.5	4.4	3.6
60-30-30 kg NPK/ha	4.0	3.4	4.7	4.0
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> (15 t/ha)	5.2	3.9	5.3	4.8
<i>Eupatorium odenophorium</i> (15 t/ha)	3.6	3.6	4.3	3.9
Mean	3.9	3.6	4.7	4.2
SE for treatment (T)	0.3	ns	0.1	0.1
SE for location (L)				0.1
SE for T × L				0.2

^aAt 12% moisture